

Participatory Development for the Rural Poor as a challenge in Tanzania.¹

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Abstract

This paper highlights some challenges in meeting the expectations of the rural poor during the implementation of the participatory development programs. Contrary to the commonly held notion that poor people are ignorant and rigid to change, the paper shows that their facilitators' behavioral and political factors constitute a significant source of development retardation. The paper recommends that a permanent and vibrant capacity-building program and information dissemination mechanisms to villagers on projects' benefits and the role of the local community are instituted, together with the village-based non-partisan development committees for addressing issues of mistrust and tension.

Keywords: Participation, spaces of participation, Opportunity and Obstacles to Development.

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1.0 Introduction

The need for participatory development in developing countries cannot be overemphasized. It is now well acknowledged that participatory development is the most important approach towards enabling communities to help themselves and sustain efforts in development work (Mathbor, 2008; Zakus et al., 1998; Sanoff, 2000). It is, therefore, a consensus among development practitioners to involve the beneficiaries, particularly the poor.

Participation is a concept whose application and definition vary depending on the context in which it is used. It is a complex concept with complications in its understanding (White et al. 1994:16). Participation can be taken as means when local people cooperate or collaborate with the externally introduced development in accomplishing a development project. Participation can also be taken as an end when people are empowered in skills acquisition, knowledge, and experience to take greater responsibility for their development trajectories (Nelson and Wright 1995). The popular definition of participation is that of Cohen and Uphoff (1977), "people's involvement in decision-making processes, implementing programs, sharing in the benefits of development programs, and in evaluating such programs." This understanding of participation is relevant to this paper which takes participation as people's involvement in decision-making processes in all stages of any development program. Development refers to a process by which the members of society increase their personal and institutional capacities to mobilize and manage resources to produce sustainable and justly distributed improvements in their quality of life consistent with their aspirations (Mathbor, 2008).

As part of the efforts to promote the participation of the people in the decision-making processes and development activities, the policy of Decentralization by Devolution has been adopted in Tanzania since 2002. The decentralization process is implemented through the Opportunities and Obstacles to Development (O&OD) approach. This official planning methodology provides an opportunity for local communities to participate fully in development planning (Fjeldstad et al., 2010).

2. Problem, methods, and materials

A study was conducted in four districts of Mainland Tanzania to examine whether O&OD methodology enhances the participation of the villagers in the development processes. The assessment of participation as the involvement of the villagers in the different spaces of participation was made in the villagers of the three districts where O&OD methodology had been

implemented and one district in which it was not implemented. The expectation was that there would be more enhanced participation in the three districts in which O&OD was implemented than where O&OD was not implemented. The theoretical thrust of this study was that O&OD should lead to more participation in decision-making. The four selected districts for the study are namely: Misungwi, Mvomero, Babati, and Mbulu.

The two districts of Mvomero and Missungwi were selected based on their participation dynamics resulting from external support to local communities. Misungwi had been under the support of the United Nations Capital Development Fund (UNCDF) for two decades; Mvomero had extensively implemented a participatory community-based Village Travel and Transport Programme. Babati and Mbulu districts in the Manyara region were selected because they share similar ecological and traditional values (both are mountainous with dominant Iraqw inhabitants). Babati district had undergone the O&OD process, but Mbulu had not.

The primary research strategy adopted was cross-sectional, using observations, interviews, and documentary analysis since the phenomenon of O&OD and participation is not readily distinguishable from the participatory practices of the village people in the day-to-day organization of their development activities (Yin 1993).

The sampling was 'participation' as a key criterion. Since the study aimed at examining how O&OD methodology had enhanced participation at the village level, participation was core, with the selection of the respondents being handled in a participatory manner by respondents themselves volunteering to be included in the sample. After the selection exercise was over, the study ended up with a total sample of 396 respondents distributed per district, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Sample Size per District

<i>District</i>	<i>No of Respondents</i>
Babati	100
Missungwi	120
Mvomero	76
Mbulu	100
Total	396

3.0 Spaces for participation

Gaventa (2007) has conceptualized space as a social product, the construction of which is considered inherent to power, to be used by people for meaningful engagement in decision-making. Therefore, the spaces for participation are arenas or opportunities for public involvement. Three spaces are identifiable, namely closed, invited, and created or claimed spaces.

In the participatory development literature, the concept of closed space refers to an exclusive domain of a group of decision-makers 'behind closed doors, and entry into these spaces is denied to outsiders (Penderis, 2012). Consequently, people are systematically excluded from the decision-making forums even if they wish to be part of the decision-makers. Closed spaces in the study area manifested in group projects, village committees, women's empowerment activities, and sector-specific projects. Such closed spaces are typically provided or captured by the elites (be they bureaucrats, experts, or elected representatives) to make decisions and provide services to the villagers (Dasgupta and Beard, 2007). Some of them are not captured as such but aim to exclude other people from promoting those perceived as powerless (such with women empowerment initiatives). However, what becomes critical is the fact that in such spaces, there is no need for broader consultation or involvement of the people.

On the other hand, invited spaces refer to opportunities for involvement and consultation. Such opportunities usually come when various authorities (local and central government, local, national or international agencies, and NGOs) call the people to participate in different development activities (Hickey and Mohan, 2007). In practice, Village General Meetings are clear invited space for participation by the villagers.

Claimed spaces for participation are those which the relatively powerless or excluded groups create for themselves; such spaces are not creations of the "goodwill" of others but created by the less powerful actors from or against the power holders, or created more autonomously by them (Gaventa, 2007). Claimed spaces could range from those created by organized community associations to those simply involving natural places where people gather to debate, discuss and resist outside of the institutionalized policy arenas.

To capture the three dimensions of participation spaces as described above, the respondents were asked if they felt there were decision-making forums or meetings in their villages which they were supposed to attend but were left out (closed space); whether they had ever participated in any decision-

making forums or meeting in their villages (invited space) and, whether there were any forums or meetings ever called out of their initiatives (claimed space).

Among the three spaces, the closed space was considered the lowest in the levels of participation. This is because the closed-out people cannot participate in any case. The invited space was considered to be in the middle as the invited people are considered less "protagonists" in participation as someone else calls them in for participation. The claimed space represented the highest step. This is highest because the people become protagonists and organize themselves for and in participation. Table 2 gives a summary of their responses for each participation space category.

4.0 Findings

Table 2: Respondents' overall Participation in Spaces

	<i>Babati</i>	<i>Mvomero</i>	<i>Misungwi</i>	<i>Mbulu</i>	<i>Overall</i>
<i>Claimed (%)</i>	40	42.1	31.6	34	36.4
<i>Invited (%)</i>	42	11.8	44.2	29	33.6
<i>Closed (%)</i>	18	45.8	24.2	37	30.0
<i>TOTAL (%)</i>	100	100	100	100	100

In Table 1, respondents had either been invited (33.6%) or claimed (36.4%) as far as development decision-making forums are concerned. Third of the respondents (30%) had a feeling of being closed out in development decision-making forums. Mvomero District leads in respondents being closed out, and so is true for claiming participation space. It was noted during the discussion that the pattern and extent of participation in Mvomero District is, to a large extent, influenced by tensions and mistrust among community members, which are, unfortunately, built along ethnic lines - the Maasai pastoralists and crop-growing communities.

To know which district is more participatory in terms of spaces of participation, a participation space index was calculated based on the weighted means, products of percent participation to various spaces, and the corresponding weight of each space. For example, Babati District had space index of 2.22, as shown in Table 3. In terms of space levels, claimed spaces are given more weight (level 3) and closed space the lowest weight (Level 1). Other districts' space indices were determined in the same manner.

Table 3: Babati Space Index

<i>Space Levels</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Weighted mean</i>
Claimed space: Level 3	40	1.2
Invited space: Level 2	42	0.84
Closed space: Level 1	18	0.18
Space index		2.22

In Table 3, space indices for the four study districts are indicated. The more participatory the district is to the development process, the higher the space index.

Table 4: Participation Space Indices

<i>Rank</i>	<i>District</i>	<i>Space index</i>
1	Babati	2.22
2	Misungwi	2.74
3	Mbulu	1.97
4	Mvomero	1.96

Mvomero District, where O&OD was conducted, has the smallest participation space index, 1.96, implying that it was relatively lower participatory in development than other study districts.

Cross-tabulating districts and the space variables of claimed, invited, and closed, gave the Chi-Square Test result of 0.000, 0.000, and 0.005, respectively, implying that there were significant differences in the levels of participation in various spaces. Misungwi district had the highest participation in all the spaces, and Mvomero had the least participation in Invited space. Cross-tabulation results for closed, invited and claimed spaces regarding gender, age, and education variables showed no significant differences in their participation. These findings conclude that concerning the variables of gender, age, and education, there are no significant differences in participation with respect to spaces.

The extent of participation in invited space, as noted in Misungwi District, needs a cautious interpretation. This is because not always the beneficiaries' priorities will be honored. For instance, although the identification of the Bujingwa market as a local development priority was made during the O&OD process, it was not their priority. It was revealed that the community's priority in the village was water supply; second, dispensary, and third, construction of the market. Disregarding this prioritization, the donor picked the construction of the Bujingwa market, which was ranked third by the community. This can be argued that participation by the community members was sought to assist implementation of the Market construction, which was already in the support portfolios of the Donor (Nelson and Wright, 1995)

Lessons can be drawn from a situation where the voices and choices of the beneficiaries are not fully considered. When the market was constructed, the community members in Bujingwa village could circumvent the officially established procedures of using the market. The District Council had sub-contracted a revenue collector for the market. The villagers had not been involved in the management of their market. People were hesitant about the new market, and only a few started to sell their crops in the market, while most of them were bypassing it by carrying their produce to other selling points. This move reduced the amount of revenue collected from the market. The revenue collector decided to put a roadblock near the market to control them. These measures against circumvention, as taken by the implementing agent of the game's rules, only resulted in a total malfunctioning of the system. Even those who had started to use the market decided to stop. This scenario presents an excellent lesson to development practitioners that for the communities to participate in development programs, it is essential that their priorities are seriously considered. This market was constructed through community involvement in 2009 following the O&OD exercise but has remained unused to date.

It was also noted that some key development decisions were made in what can be termed as "Private spaces," which are purposely established by corrupt leaders for closing out people in decision making. The following remark by a desperate respondent from Mvomero gives this revelation:

Only people with influence and close to the leaders can be told what things will be done. Some of us are seen as obstacles to our selfish gains and, therefore, are not invited. Of course, they know it very well that if we know their schemes, they will never be at peace!

Similarly, in Babati District, in line with the prevailing politics of isolation, one party leader in Baashay village plainly said that 'closing out the so called "trouble makers" was one of the ways of politically suffocating their opponents for whom the doors will always remain closed.

The lessons which can be learned from Mvomero and Babati are in some ways different from Misungwi District. In the latter case, the donors limited the effectiveness of community participation in development projects. In Mvomero District, on the other hand, it is the village leadership that tended to exclude a certain section of the community. This is a behavioral problem of the very people expected to facilitate development participation. This 'participation manipulation' is partly explained by Marsland (2006), who observed that there were at least two contradictory meanings of participation circulating amongst development workers in Tanzania: One concerning "empowerment" and the facilitation of local decision-making, which is

associated with international development discourse; and the other, concerning the obligation of Tanzanian citizens to contribute to the development of the nation in line with the philosophy of Julius Nyerere. She found that the practices of Tanzanian and expatriate development workers are distanced enough for these disparate versions of participation.

The assumption behind any genuine participatory approach to development is that sustainable development is possible once the capacities of local people (individuals and groups) are enhanced to improve their own lives and take greater control over their destinies (Chambers, 1994; Cornwall, 2000). Although the assumption is self-evident, it demands a considerable change in the process of governance, socio-political relationships, and who participates, controls, and is empowered by the development process. Subsequently, there is a need for clarity, well in advance, to the following questions as put forward by Wild, L. et al. (2015): what kind of participation is under consideration? This entails knowing categorically who participates, why, and how. In the absence of other relevant information on who participated in the O&OD exercise, how they participated and their motives behind and how it was facilitated, and the capacity of facilitators in terms of skills and experiences, it isn't easy to judge whether O&OD is effective participation tool or not.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper has discussed three spaces of participation, namely the invited, closed, and claimed spaces. It has been argued that among the three kinds of spaces in which the rural people can participate, the claimed space is a dominant arena of participation in the study area followed by invited spaces and, lastly, closed spaces. The main participation forums include official village meetings, group projects, village committees, women's empowerment activities, sector-specific projects, and "private arenas ."The people in the different districts were engaged in these spaces differently. It has been indicated that to establish whether or not the O&OD methodology enhances the participation of the villagers in the development processes in Tanzania; a thorough analysis is necessary about who participated, how they participated, what the motives for participation were, how participation was facilitated, and how capable the facilitators were in terms of skills and experiences.

The primary assumption was that implementation of O&OD methodology was essential for effective community participation, which could have manifested itself in communities being more involved in the invited and claimed spaces. The underlying factors for some community members being

closed out of decision-making forums include but are not limited to; cultural factors such as corrupt leaders and favoritism, undemocratic leadership, politics of isolation, ignorance of their rights, and absence of local democratic institutions, particularly the media.

Claimed spaces come about as a result of three factors: First, when poor members of the community feel closed out of official decision-making forums; second, when they think their priorities are not honored in the invited forums and third when they feel there are injustices in the society such as corruption among the leaders.

To ensure effective community participation, it is recommended that:

First, the Ministry responsible for local governments establishes a permanent and vibrant capacity-building program to ensure facilitation skills to District and Ward O&OD Facilitation Teams are enhanced. Members of the facilitation teams must be conversant with the relevant tools and methods of O&OD. Facilitators at all levels have to undergo a similar training process to cascade to community members effectively.

Second, the Local Government Authorities should assist Village Governments in establishing a sustainable information management system. The experience from this study shows that successful implementation of O&OD does not entirely depend on the ability and commitment of facilitators alone. There are also other local political, cultural, institutional, and behavioral factors. These need to be addressed along with the facilitation of the process itself. Permanent and vibrant information dissemination mechanisms to both villagers and facilitators must be in place for information sharing. Such mechanisms could include a district-based capacity building program for villages on governance issues, annual or biannual publications meant to share basic development facts and information, and a Radio/TV program.

Third, the Local Government Authorities should assist Village Governments in establishing non-partisan, village-based conflict resolution committees to address issues of mistrust and tension among the people and, fourth, the Ministry responsible for local governments should establish exposure program to local leaders on strategic leadership, good governance, conflict management, communication skills and teamwork.

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